

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101096405	Acronym	UP2030	
Full Title	Urban Planning and design ready for 2030			
Start Date	01/01/2023	Duration	36 months	
Project Website	http://up2030-he.eu/			
Deliverable	D6.1 – Dissemination and Communication strategy 1			
Work Package	WP6 – UP-TAKING - Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Sustainability of UP2030			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/03/2023	Actual	31/03/2023
Nature	R — Document, report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public	
Lead Beneficiary	UCCRN			
Author(s)	Cristina Visconti, Anna Baldassarre, (UCCRN); Evangelos Kosmidis (DreVen); Eugenia Covernton, Louise Francis (MfC); Elena Petsani, Luca Arbau (ICLEI)			
Reviewer(s)	Evangelos Kosmidis (DreVen SRL); Catalina Diaz, Sarah Walz (Fraunhofer)			
Abstract	<p>This deliverable presents the Target-Driven Dissemination and Communication Strategy of UP2030 project. The document is structured in 6 sections describing: roadmap of strategy and key players (section 1); dissemination plan, objectives and activities, identification of the target audience and messages (section 2); communication plan objectives, tools and activities, identification of the target audience (section 3); gender-sensitive and inclusive strategy for dissemination and communication (section 4); monitoring activities and key performance indicators (section 5); synthesis of main contents and further steps (section 6).</p> <p>The purpose of this deliverable is to guide the effective dissemination and communication of the project’s goals and objectives, and the further steps needed for implementation.</p>			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
0.1	22/02/2023	Draft	Design of table of contents	DreVen, UCCRN
0.2	10/03/2023	Draft	Objectives and Contents	UCCRN, DreVen
0.3	23/03/2023	Draft Review	Derivable Description and contents review	UCCRN, DreVen, MfC Fraunhofer, ICLEI
1.0	31/03/2023	Final	Final version the deliverable	UCCRN

[Disclaimer](#)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EUROPEAN UNION or the EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

[Copyright message](#)

© UP2030 Consortium, 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Contents

Executive summary.....	6
Acronyms	8
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Purpose and Scope	9
1.2 Document Structure	11
1.3 Roadmap.....	11
2 Dissemination Plan	15
2.1 Dissemination Objectives	15
2.2 Dissemination target audience and messages.....	16
2.2.1 Dissemination Activities	21
2.2.2 Dissemination Guidelines.....	23
2.3 Individual Dissemination Plans.....	24
2.4 Synergies with the other projects and Initiatives	25
3 Communication Plan.....	28
3.1 Communication Objectives	28
3.2 Communication target audiences and messages	28
3.3 Communication Tools and Activities.....	30
3.3.1 Visual Identity	30
3.3.2 Project Templates.....	34
3.3.3 Social Media Presence.....	37
3.3.4 Website.....	38
3.3.5 Events & Publications	39
3.3.7 Press Kit	39
3.3.8 Newsletter & Press release	40
4 Gender dimension in UP230 dissemination and communication strategy.....	41
4.1 Communication teams	41
4.2 Communication channels.....	41
4.3 Gender-sensitive language and images	42
4.4 Stakeholder engagement	43
4.5 Monitoring and evaluation.....	43

5 Dissemination and Communication Indicators 44

6 Conclusions 46

References 47

Figures

Figure 1 : The 5UP-approach conceptual framework 7

Figure 2: Diagram of project phases and WPs 7

Figure 3 UP2030 Dissemination and Communication Roadmap 14

Figure 4 UP2030 Publications&Events 23

Figure 5 UP2030 Individual Dissemination Plan..... 24

Figure 6 Up 2030 Individual channels of partners 25

Figure 7 UP2030 Potential Synergies Database 27

Figure 8 UP2030 colour palette 31

Figure 9 UP2030 logos (main version and simplified version) 32

Figure 10 EU emblem 33

Figure 11 UP2030 banner 33

Figure 12 UP2030 deliverable template..... 34

Figure 13 UP2030 presentation template..... 35

Figure 14 UP2030 press release template 35

Figure 15 UP2030 blog article template 35

Figure 16 UP2030 Consent form 36

Figure 17 UP2030 General use template 37

Figure 18 UP2030 LinkedIn account..... 38

Figure 19 UP2030 Twitter account..... 38

Figure 20 Global Social Media Statistics — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights 42

Tables

Table 1 UP2030 Target Groups for Dissemination 21

Table 2 UP2030 Target Groups for Communication 29

Table 4 Communication activities KPIs. 44

Table 5 Dissemination activities KPIs. 45

Executive summary

UP2030 aims at supporting cities in driving their socio-technical transitions to achieve their climate neutrality targets. The project aims to develop an innovative methodology that cities can adopt to engage meaningfully with the EU Mission Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, comprising consistent policy development, upskilling in state-of-the-art approaches, prototyping upgrades, and upscaling city-wide neutrality actions. The project's approach focuses on enhancing the liveability of urban communities by mainstreaming the climate neutrality agenda using urban planning and design as a vehicle.

In particular, the Target-Driven Communication and Dissemination Strategy presented here is the baseline of one of the 5 interlinked phases of the UP2030 approach (**5UP-approach**) defined to accelerate the implementation pace in many cities, upscale solutions and respond to the climate emergency.

UP2030 proposes the 5UP-approach for activating cities and stakeholders in which the Communication and Dissemination Strategy presented here sets the base for the **UP-TAKING phase [WP6] in which the project will support the uptake through knowledge transfer by offering the project's services to the Mission and extend the project's twinning to create long-lasting Communities of Practice.**

According to UP2030 approach, this deliverable aims at outlining a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy for the project which will primarily target the project's end-users (cities and citizens) and solutions providers, while also attempting to attract additional stakeholders to maximise the impacts and bring concrete solutions for climate-neutrality action.

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy points to ensure effective communication of the project results to both the scientific community, and policymakers, facilitating the exploitation of the project outcomes by promoting their uptake and use by relevant city stakeholders. The strategy is conceived as a roadmap to foster the UP2030 goals of co-development and implementation of science-based practical tools and methods that guide cities to deliver across the values of equity, resilience, neutrality, and sustainability.

This document significantly contributes to the delivery of innovative knowledge co-produced by the diversity of the project's partners (scientists, practitioners, policy and decision-makers, city officials) with the broader objectives to address societal challenges through research and innovation activities.

Figure 1 : The SUP-approach conceptual framework

Figure 2: Diagram of project phases and WPs

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
SO	Specific Objectives
T	Task
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

UP2030 Communication and Dissemination Strategy aims at effectively and efficiently communicating the project's findings and results to the target audience, including cities, policymakers, experts, and the general public. The goal is to create awareness and understanding of the project's objectives, outcomes, and impact, and promote the adoption and implementation of the project's methodology in cities across Europe. The strategy as part of the **WP6** dedicated to the **UP-TAKING phase of the project [Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Sustainability of UP2030]** supports the uptake through knowledge transfer by offering the project's services to the Mission and extend the project's twinning to create long-lasting Communities of Practice.

The current document has been developed considering EU indications for dissemination and communication of Horizon Europe Programme present in the [Guidelines of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities of Horizon Europe Programme \(EU 2022\)](#), in the [EU REGULATION 2021/695 2021 establishing Horizon Europe-Article 39](#) and in the webinar session [Webinar session: Dissemination & Exploitation in Horizon Europe \(9 June 2021\)](#) [1,2,3].

Although dissemination and communication are complementary approaches that work together to maximize the impact of UP2030, they point to reach different target audiences. Dissemination ensures that the results are made widely available and can be used to advance knowledge and innovation, while communication helps to create awareness about the project and its objectives.

Dissemination targets specific audiences, such as the scientific community, policy and decision makers, stakeholders, and potential investors, and starts only after the project results become available. The purpose of dissemination is to transfer and circulate knowledge to those who can make the best use of it and further build on the project's results to maximize impacts.

Communication, on the other hand, aims to reach a broad audience, including non-specialists, and starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its lifespan. The purpose of communication is to promote the project, create public awareness, and explain the research in an accessible way through public visibility of the project results using accessible language and media. While communication and dissemination both aim to promote the project's results, they differ in their timing, target audience, and focus.

The broader scope of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy will include identifying the key stakeholders, channels, and messages that will enable the project to reach its target audience. The strategy outlines a comprehensive plan for disseminating the project's results, including publications, reports, workshops, webinars, conferences, and a plan for communicating to a broader public through social media campaigns. The strategy also addresses how the project will engage with policy and decision makers, experts, stakeholders and citizens to maximize the impact of the project's findings and to ensure its sustainability, including specific attention to the gender dimension and the inclusivity. The Communication and Dissemination Strategy is here developed to lead to a long-term scientific and societal impact of the project.

Accordingly, this deliverable moves from the integration of UP2030 specific objectives (SO) into a comprehensive roadmap for dissemination and communication as tool that actively contribute to deliver project's main outcomes and to accomplish the main goal of **WP6 [UP-Taking]** that allows meaningful dissemination towards replication, offering the project's solutions to the Mission cities and beyond.

Main **UP2030 specific objectives** are:

- **SO1.** Engage the cities' stakeholder ecosystem in the mapping of their needs and baseline assessments, to co-design neutrality visions that synergistically deliver on the values of justice, resilience, sustainability and neutrality.
- **SO2.** Develop implementation roadmaps, customise tools and methods for the delivery of prototyping actions in the testbed neighborhood environments.
- **SO3.** Make neighborhoods more liveable, inclusive, and equitable by leveraging the neutrality transition
- **SO4.** Guarantee city-wide upscale of solutions by shaping the enabling governance arrangements, updating policy instruments and promoting relevant financing mechanisms.
- **SO5.** Share broadly the lessons of success and levers to overcoming implementation barriers. Support replication beyond the project's scale in collaboration with the Mission while demonstrating how the solutions contribute to European policy and strategy implementation.

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy will be aligned with the project's objectives to achieve the following outcomes:

- Create awareness and understanding of the project's objectives, methodology, and outcomes among the target audience.
- Promote the adoption and implementation of the project's methodology in cities across Europe.
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration between cities, policymakers, and experts on the subject of climate-neutral and smart cities.
- Contribute to the achievement of the EU Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by supporting cities in driving socio-technical transitions to achieve climate neutrality targets.
- Ensure the sustainability and long-term impact of the project's methodology beyond the project's duration.

Overall, the Communication and Dissemination Strategy will play a critical role in achieving the project's objectives and ensuring its impact on the target audience. By effectively communicating the project's findings and outcomes, the strategy will contribute to the creation of a more sustainable and climate-neutral European cities and support the specific project objective of sharing broadly the lessons of success and leveraging the up-scaling of the proposed solutions through their implementation and synergies with the other projects of the Mission.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- Section 1 - INTRODUCTION: description of the purpose and scope of the document, its structure, roadmap of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy and key players
- Section 2 - DISSEMINATION PLAN: outline of the dissemination objectives and activities, identification of the target audience and messages, definition of individual dissemination plan and dissemination guideline for partners
- Section 3 - COMMUNICATION PLAN: outline of objectives identification of the target audience and messages, tools and activities
- Section 4 - GENDER DIMENSION: gender-sensitive and inclusive strategy for dissemination and communication
- Section 5 - DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION INDICATORS: description of the monitoring activities and key performance indicators
- Section 6 - CONCLUSION: synthesis of main contents and further steps

1.3 Roadmap

The UP2030 roadmap for the Target-Driven Communication and Dissemination Strategy outlines the plan for effectively sharing project results and engaging with relevant stakeholders and target audience throughout the project lifecycle. It describes the *why*, *how*, and *what* of the strategy adopting a step-by-step approach in accord with the Guidelines of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities of Horizon Europe Programme (EU 2022) [1] and it is articulated in three sections. The roadmap steps are related to the project timeframe as presented in [Figure 3](#).

WHY: The *why* of the roadmap explains the objectives and goals of the dissemination and communication strategy. It includes a clear explanation of the intended impact of the project and how the strategy will contribute to achieving these goals by. The *why* refers to:

- Increasing awareness and understanding of the project's objectives and activities among relevant stakeholders and general public.
- Promoting the uptake and use of the project's results by policy and decision makers, and other relevant city stakeholders.
- Ensuring that the project's results are communicated in a transparent, open, and accessible manner, while respecting any confidentiality and data protection requirements and the gender equality recommendations, specifically included in this document.

This roadmap section is structured around three main key points:

1. Focusing on the overall objectives of UP2030
2. Setting dissemination objectives
3. Setting communication objectives

HOW: The *how* of the roadmap refers to the steps engaged by the project to individuate key players, target audience and messages that need to orient the Communication and Dissemination Strategy. The **how** refers to:

- To outline the key messages, target audiences, and communication channels according to different stages of the project.
- To identify key players intended as relevant stakeholders that will be engaged by the partners through the different stages of the project. Indications will be provided in particular for the cities engaged in the consortium of the project that will play a key role in defining relevant and local city stakeholders that will be impacted by the demonstrating pilots.
- To individuate opportunities on how to build synergies with other projects and initiatives, giving attention to the specific potentialities offered by the collaboration with the other projects Mission's.
- To consider gender dimension considered before, during and after all dissemination and communication activities to ensure that the strategy of the project as a whole is gender-sensitive and inclusive.

This roadmap section is structured around five main key points:

4. Defining the Roadmap
5. Identifying Target Audience
6. Defining Messages
7. Building synergies with other project and initiatives
8. Considering Gender dimension and Inclusivity

WHAT: The *what* of the roadmap describes the specific outputs and activities of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy that will be undertaken to achieve the identified objectives. It outlines the dissemination plan and the communication that details the types of materials that will be produced (such as reports, policy briefs, scientific publications, infographic), the use of various communication channels, such as social media, newsletters, press releases, webinars, and conferences. It includes the monitoring phase based on key performance indicators (KPIs) for each dissemination and communication activity and implementation measures. The **what** refers to:

- Publishing of scientific and technical publications
- Organizing webinars and conferences to share project results and engage with relevant stakeholders.
- Developing social media content to promote the project and engage with the broader community.
- Creating a project website that provides information on the project's objectives, activities, and results.
- Developing policy briefs that outline the implications of the project's results for policymakers and industry.
- Creating infographics and videos that provide accessible and engaging summaries of the project's findings.

This roadmap section is structured around five main key points:

- 9. Preparing Dissemination Tools and Activities
- 10. Preparing Dissemination Tools and Activities
- 11. Sharing Dissemination Timeplan
- 12. Sharing Communication Timeplan
- 13. Monitoring through dissemination and communication indicators

The roadmap for a Communication and Dissemination Strategy contributes the generation of a comprehensive and integrated plan that outlines the why, how, and what of the strategy, and that allows a regularly monitoring and evaluation to ensure its effectiveness in achieving the desired outcomes throughout the lifespan of the project.

Figure 3 UP2030 Dissemination and Communication Roadmap

Key players for the Communication and Dissemination Strategy effectiveness and for the UP-TAKING phase of the project are identified to be the international network organizations part of the UP2030 consortium (UCCRN, ICLEI, RCities) allowing the project to disseminate its findings to an extensive pool of cities, practitioners and scientists (in particular reach the scientific community, SMEs and experts in urban planning and design, and related disciplines) in EU and beyond, and the relevant local stakeholder's ecosystem within the 11 UP2030 piloting cities.

The UP-TAKING of the UP2030 solutions will be leveraged by the UCCRN, ICLEI and RCities networks and partnerships, expanding the outreach and high replicability potential of the knowledge components and tools. The dissemination activities developed by these partners are also related to their contributions to WP6 [T6.3 Exploitation, Standardisation and Market Readiness; T6.4 Collaboration with the Mission and related projects] and to other WPs in which several dissemination activities will take place (such as training, workshops, joint initiatives and events). In particular, WP4 and WP5 will contribute to the dissemination activities through the following tasks:

- **WP4 [UP-GRADING: Piloting and demonstrating]** T4.1 Pilots coordination & implementation of solutions & processes and T4.4 Cross-pilot exchange Community of Practice and Strategic Learning
- **WP5 [UP-SCALING: Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making]** T5.2 Replication and Transferability Packages and T5.4 Training program for climate neutral and smart cities

2 Dissemination Plan

Effective dissemination is a crucial component of high-impact research, and coordination is a key particularly in a project such as UP2030 that involves a high number of partners, multiple groups of audiences and stakeholders. In order to maximize the impact of research outcomes and engage with key stakeholders, a systematic approach has been proposed to effectively achieve the planned dissemination activities throughout the duration of the project.

Key target audiences are identified, customizing messaging and content for each category, and leveraging a variety of communication and dissemination channels to reach them. Partners and stakeholders will work closely to co-create knowledge and share perspectives, as well as to promote fair and inclusive practices for knowledge production and dissemination. UP2030 will focus on identifying the entry points to “converse” with different groups, as their primary drivers might not always be climate neutrality per se.

The UP2030 dissemination and communication plan is based on the guidelines provided by the European Commission for Horizon Europe, which recommend making research results publicly accessible to a broad range of stakeholders, including authorities, industry, policymakers, sectors of interest, and civil society. This helps maximizing the impact of the results, allowing other researchers to build upon them, contributing to the advancement of the state of the art, and making scientific results a common good.

Ultimately, effective dissemination is about creating transparency and visibility around research outcomes, and building engagement and support for the project's goals and objectives. Therefore, UP2030 is committed to adopting Open Science practices, particularly open data practices, to ensure easy and wide access to the project outputs for researchers and other stakeholders relevant to the project's domain.

UP2030 will utilize the available resources mentioned on the [Horizon Europe - Dissemination and exploitation](#) guide to achieve maximum impact [5]. Therefore, the UP2030 dissemination strategy will take into consideration European Commission free-of-charge services to support dissemination and exploitation activities (for example: [Open Research Europe platform](#), [Innovation radar](#), [Horizon Results platform](#), etc) [6].

2.1 Dissemination Objectives

The general objectives for dissemination actions are the following:

- Creating an effective communication workflow both for internal and external communication. This will involve identifying appropriate dissemination channels, establishing communication protocols, and ensuring that dissemination is timely, accurate, and accessible.
- Ensuring participation in international and national events, conferences and other meetings which are crucial for the representation of UP2030 results and presentation of deliverables results. This will involve identifying relevant events and conferences, preparing presentations, and ensuring that project team members attend these events to represent the project and share its results.

- Creating transparency and visibility of the project results. This will involve developing a project website, publishing project results in relevant journals and publications, and making project reports and other materials publicly available.

The dissemination strategy targets a variety of audiences, and messages and content will be customized according to the target groups. This is essential for raising awareness of the project outcomes and achieving the desired impact.

In the context of UP2030, the following **SO** of the dissemination plan are to be pursued throughout the project lifetime:

- **Maximizing the impact of the project activities:** Identification of key stakeholders and developing targeted communication strategies to reach them.
- **Co-creating valuable scientific knowledge based on co-production with stakeholders and communities:** development of partnerships with stakeholders and involving them in the project's activities.
- **Sharing novel perspectives developed by the project with scientific communities and stakeholders:** development of targeted dissemination strategies to reach these audiences and sharing the project's results through publications, conferences, and other relevant channels.
- **Raising the awareness of stakeholders (in particular decision-makers) about the tools implemented by the project to achieve climate-neutrality:** development of targeted communication strategies to reach decision-makers and sharing the project's results through relevant channels.
- **Encouraging fair practices for knowledge production and dissemination:** ensure that gender inclusivity and consideration of intersectional factors in the dissemination practices are taking into account by project's partners and engaged stakeholders
- **Leveraging communication measures to support inclusiveness in dissemination:** development of communication strategies that are culturally sensitive, accessible to different language groups, and that take into account the needs of different stakeholder groups, gender and intersectionality dimensions.

2. 2. Dissemination target audience and messages

Delivering the right message to the right target audience in the right format, at the right time, is essential for the dissemination of the project. To this end, it is crucial to identify the appropriate audience for each message and content. As the UP2030 project covers different areas and sectors adjusting channels according to the stakeholders, the target audience is of high importance.

The UP2030 dissemination and communication plan includes workshops, meetings with regional partners, participation in conferences, organization of conferences. Workshops and conferences aim at providing attractive and useful means for engagement across our targeted stakeholders groups.

In the first phase of the dissemination strategy, it is crucial to identify the target groups who may be interested in the UP2030 project. This involved considering factors such as interests, expertise, levels of

influence or decision-making power, and other relevant criteria. The mapping process also took into account any existing networks or relationships that the project partners have with potential stakeholders and considered how best to leverage these connections to engage and communicate with the target groups.

Key to creating impact is structuring outputs in ways that stakeholders can readily use to navigate the complexity of urban development. The UP2030 project is targeted at specific stakeholder groups, and possible dissemination actions on different levels have been identified to reach each of the following target audiences:

- ***Cities and networks***
- ***Policy & decision-makers***
- ***NGOs***
- ***Mission & associated projects***
- ***Scientific Community***
- ***Urban planning experts and SMEs***
- ***Local institutions and territorial agencies***
- ***International standardisation bodies and research infrastructures***

Key messages are adapted to each target audience, and will be refined over the course of the project.

UP2030 main messages related to target audiences:

- **Cities and networks** → Robust and replicable methods to identify needs, assess baselines, address barriers and create visions for a just and resilient transition towards climate neutrality by 2030.
- **Policy & decision-makers** → Ready to use data, information and white papers to create an evidence base for integrative policies on urban planning and design, energy efficiency and climate adaptation.
- **NGOs** → Innovative tools and methods to encourage inclusive citizen participation and promote citizens to adopt sustainable behaviors to minimise their environmental footprint and contribute to the cities' transitions.
- **Mission & associated projects** → UP2030 and associated Mission projects will engage in deep collaboration to identify common narratives and provide tested solutions and best practices to contribute to the Mission's vision.
- **Scientific Community** → Cost-effective socio-technical solutions based on an innovative framework for better urban planning and design which will open the path for further research opportunities.
- **Urban planning, experts and SMEs** → Solutions which address impacts on climate and the environment while fostering trust with consumers and investors through environmental accountability.
- **Local institutions and territorial agencies** → UP2030 can benefit local institutions and territorial agencies, as the project aims to provide innovative and sustainable solutions for urban

development. UP2030 value the partnership and collaboration to boost innovation in climate neutrality strategies for resilient, livable, and equitable cities.

- **International standardisation bodies and research infrastructures** → UP2030 makes the participatory approaches and social impact assessments of neutrality interventions a standard practice. UP2030 data and tools validated and made openly available for research and policymaking.

UP2030's Target-Driven Strategy is outlined in the following tables in which the different types of audience, relevant bodies, key messages and dissemination opportunities are identified.

Target	Description	Relevant bodies	Key message	Dissemination opportunities
A. Cities and networks	This audience includes municipal governments, city managers, and networks of cities or urban areas.	Covenant of Mayors (EU), Global Covenant of Mayors, ICLEI, Resilient Cities Network, Eurocities, EnergyCities, Climate- KIC, C40, Cities Alliance, UN-Habitat	"UP2030 provides robust and replicable methods to identify needs, assess baselines, address barriers and create visions for a just and resilient transition towards climate neutrality by."2030	UP2030 will disseminate its findings to an extensive pool of cities (e.g., ICLEI and RCities member cities). Lessons from UP2030 will be extracted and offered in "replication and transferability packages" to cities outside the project. For more effective dissemination, the project will also develop a Training Programme on "urban planning and design for climate neutral and smart cities" which will include open access resources as legacy. Moreover, cities wishing to engage in more depth with certain UP2030 solutions will be able to do so through the Service Platform of UP2030. To reach this audience, activities might include participating in city and urban planning conferences, partnering with local governments on pilot projects, and sharing research outcomes with urban planning associations and networks.
B. Policy- & decision-makers	This audience includes local, regional, national and international policy-makers who may be able to implement changes based on the research outcomes. Policy and decision-makers refer to individuals or groups who have the authority to make and implement policies that impact society. These may include government officials, elected	Committee of the Regions, Major Cities of Europe, ERRIN, FEDARENE, ETIP Smart Networks for Energy Transition, DG ENV, DG ENER, DG CLIMA, DG MOVE, national governments / ministries.	UP2030 provides ready to use data, information and white papers to create an evidence base for integrative policies on urban planning and design, energy efficiency and climate adaptation".	Analytical insights of the project results will be disseminated through the preparation of policy briefs throughout the project targeting policymakers and public administrators in the sector of urban planning and design. Consortium partners have a vast experience in providing consultations for better decision-making, thus the policy briefs will include information on addressing barriers, leveraging institutional resources, etc., regarding the implementation of innovative technologies in better urban planning and design practices. To reach this audience, activities might include presenting research

	representatives, regulatory agencies, and other stakeholders who have a role in shaping policy decisions.			findings to policy-making bodies, engaging with political representatives through targeted outreach efforts, and collaborating with advocacy groups or think tanks to raise awareness of the project's goals and objectives.
C. NGOs	This audience includes non-governmental organizations who work on related issues or who may be able to support the project's goals.	URBACT, SMART CITY HUB, Urbanistes	UP2030 provides innovative tools and methods to encourage inclusive citizen participation and promote citizens to adopt sustainable behaviours to minimise their environmental footprint and contribute to the cities' transitions".	To reach this audience, activities might include partnering with relevant NGOs on outreach or awareness-raising campaigns, presenting research findings at NGO conferences or events, and engaging in targeted outreach efforts to build relationships with relevant organizations. The following activities can be undertaken: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partnering with NGOs to support common objectives and share project updates with them - Organizing joint events or webinars to share information and gather feedback - Creating easily accessible and understandable project materials such as reports, fact sheets, and infographics, to help NGOs spread awareness about the project among their members and stakeholders.
D. Mission & associated projects	This audience includes other research or development projects that may be related to the project's goals.	RTD-HE-MissionCities, NetZeroCities	"UP2030 and associated Mission projects will engage in deep collaboration to identify common narratives and provide tested solutions and best practices to contribute to the Mission's vision".	The project plans to create synergies with the Mission projects (and other EU outlets/marketplaces) to optimise use of resources and maximise impact - e.g., existing connections with NetZeroCities will be leveraged to contribute approaches to the Mission's Platform as well as seek consistency with the Climate City Contracts. Lastly, UP2030 will demonstrate how the proposed approaches tangibly contribute to relevant EU policies and strategies.
E. Scientific Community	This audience includes other researchers and academics who may be interested in the project's goals or outcomes. Other professionals who are actively engaged in scientific research and development.	Aqua Research Collaboration, BDV A/DAIRO, Association of European Operational Research Societies, European Energy Research Alliance	"UP2030 provides cost-effective socio-technical solutions based on an innovative framework for better urban planning and design which will open the path for further research opportunities".	Scientific communities can provide valuable feedback, insights, and collaboration opportunities. To reach and communicate with this audience, activities such as publishing research findings in peer-reviewed journals, presenting at academic conferences and workshops, and networking with relevant academic institutions and research groups can be

				undertaken. Additionally, creating opportunities for collaboration and knowledge-sharing through online platforms, such as webinars or discussion forums, can also be effective in engaging the scientific community.
F. Urban planning experts and SMEs	This audience includes urban planning professionals and small and medium-sized enterprises who may be interested in implementing the research outcomes.	ISOCARP, UCCRN (Global)	"UP2030 provides solutions which address impacts on climate and the environment while fostering trust with consumers and investors through environmental accountability".	<p>The following activities can be undertaken:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizing workshops and training sessions for urban planning experts and SMEs to showcase the project's findings and tools that can support sustainable urban development. - Collaborating with urban planning associations and other industry groups to disseminate project information and best practices. - Providing tools to urban planning experts and SMEs to implement sustainable urban practices. - Developing case studies and success stories to showcase the project's impact on sustainable urban development to urban planning experts and SMEs.
G. Local institutions and territorial agencies	Local institutions and territorial agencies refer to the governing bodies and organizations that are responsible for managing the local territories and providing services to the citizens in the area.	Covenant of Mayors (EU), Global Covenant of Mayors, ICLEI, Resilient Cities Network, Eurocities, EnergyCities, Climate- KIC, C40, Cities Alliance, UN-Habitat	"UP2030 can benefit local institutions and territorial agencies, as the project aims to provide innovative and sustainable solutions for urban development. UP2030 value the partnership and collaboration. We believe that through collaboration and innovation, we can create cities that are resilient, livable, and equitable for all."	<p>To reach this audience, activities might include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize workshops or meetings to inform local institutions and territorial agencies about the project objectives and benefits for their community. - Provide regular updates on project progress and outcomes, and seek their feedback and suggestions. - Engage them in project activities, such as data collection, analysis, and decision-making processes. - Collaborate with them to integrate the project outcomes into their policies and program.

<p>H. International standardisation bodies and research infrastructures</p>	<p>This audience includes organizations and institutions that are involved in the development and implementation of international standards and research infrastructures.</p>	<p>OGC, ISO, Cloud, EOSC, EGI, GAIA-X, DG INFRA</p>	<p>“UP2030 makes the participatory approaches and social impact assessments of neutrality interventions standard practice”; “UP2030 data and tools validated and open for research and policy”.</p>	<p>To effectively communicate with this audience, the following activities can be undertaken:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The team can present the project's objectives and findings at conferences and meetings organized by these bodies, - Publish articles that focus on UP2030's research and innovation achievements in relevant international journals. - Conducting workshops and training programs.
--	---	---	---	--

Table 1 UP2030 Target Groups for Dissemination

2.2.1 Dissemination Activities

An effective dissemination strategy will bundle input from the whole UP2030 project team across the lifespan of the project and will raise awareness about UP2030 results at national and international levels. The progress about the dissemination will be documented in the UP2030 Dissemination & Communication Reports (D6.3; D6.5; D6.5) for which DreVen is responsible. In these reports the project's dissemination activities and their impact on stakeholders will be summarized.

The dissemination takes into consideration the Open Science Policy under the European Commission adopting open data practices in order to guarantee easy and wide access to the project outputs to researchers as well as to other stakeholders relevant to the project’s domain. Open Research Europe and other open review platforms will be considered for UP2030 publications. Suitable and trusted repositories will be investigated via OpenAIRE, the Registry of Open Access Repositories, and the Directory of Open Access Repositories. A High use of UP2030 scientific knowledge generation will be promoted especially through scientific publications: at least 30 publications referring to UP2030.

A variety of **dissemination activities** will be carried out during the lifespan of UP2030:

- **Scientific Publications**

UP2030 will use scientific publications as a means of dissemination to showcase its technical knowledge and scientific achievements. Open access will be provided to all scientific publications of UP2030’s results by featuring in peer-reviewed journals through immediately available open access publishing (‘gold’ open access) or within a period of 6 months through self-archiving (‘green’ open access). The decision will be based on the publisher and law regulations as mentioned in the GA, the scope of the article (results it shares) as well as the partners who have contributed to the publication. All publications will be allocated to the partners participating in these publications.

[Open Research Europe](#) and other open review platforms will be considered for UP2030 publications. Suitable and trusted repositories will be investigated via OpenAIRE, the [Registry of Open Access Repositories](#), and the [Directory of Open Access Repositories](#).

Scientific Journals and Conferences considered for the dissemination include (but are no limited to):

- **Peer-reviewed Scientific Journals:** [Int. Journal of Urban Planning and Smart Cities](#), [Cities, Planning Practice & Research](#), [Int. Journal of Urban Planning and Development](#), [Journal of Urban Affairs](#), [Sustainable Cities and Society](#), [Journal of Environmental Management](#), [Environmental Research: Infrastructure and Sustainability](#), [Int. Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health](#), [Int. Journal of Sustainable Energy](#), [Citizen Science: Theory and Practice](#), [Science of the Total Environment](#), [Frontiers in Sustainable Cities](#)
- **Scientific Conferences:** [Urban Affairs Association Conference](#), [AESOP Annual Congress](#), [RC21 Urban and Regional Development Conference](#), [Int. Conference on Urban Drainage](#), [European Climate Change Adaptation Conference](#), [Urban Future](#), [Int. Conference on Urban Health](#), [Energy Cities Annual Conference](#), [IEEE Int. Smart Cities Conference](#), [Child in the City Int. Conference](#), [European Urban Resilience Forum](#)
- **Technical Publications**

Technical results will be disseminated through blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogues, books or any other outlets for technology providers, as well as publications related to the case study domains under consideration. Excellent examples of this kind of contribution are journal such as: [Applied Sciences](#), [IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters](#), [European Journal of Operational Research](#), [Computers & Industrial Engineering](#), [Journal of Simulation](#), [Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments](#), [UCCRN publications](#).
- **Workshops and Trainings**

In the lifespan of the project, consortium partners will participate in and organise relevant workshops and webinars as a means of knowledge transfer, capacity building, wider outreach and sustainability. Training sessions on the use of the project's solutions, the development of climate action plans and climate risk assessments for cities, resilient and nature-based solutions for sustainable urban planning and design will also be carried out. The "Training program for climate neutral and smart cities", which is part of WP5 and Task 5.4 led by UIC with the contribution of UCCRN, will be a key component of the dissemination activities.
- **Joint Activities with relevant Initiatives**

To further amplify and maximise the impact and outreach of the project's solutions and to achieve their integration to other cities beyond the consortium, joint dissemination activities will be carried out with relevant initiatives. Ongoing Horizon Europe projects which see the participation of UP2030 partners represent a relevant opportunity to pool resources and organize dedicated joint activities. Project partners have already strong cooperation with ongoing relevant partnerships, networks and bodies, indicatively including [NetZeroCities](#), [Cities Alliance](#), [UN-Habitat \(World Urban Campaign Urban Thinkers Campus\)](#), [Eurocities](#), [EnergyCities](#), [BDA](#), [DGNB](#), [Covenant of Mayors](#), [ECSA](#), etc.
- **Source Code Repository**

UP2030 will make accessible its software repositories through well-known distributed source code platforms in order to encourage a transparent and open-source culture. Indicative well-established

repositories are [GitHub](#) and [Bitbucket](#). Links to such platforms will be made available through the project’s website. A specific focus will be devoted to integration of UP2030 data in open platforms such as [European Science Open Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) and [Copernicus CDS](#).

○ **Policy briefs**

Analytical insights of the project results will be disseminated through the preparation of policy briefs throughout the project targeting policymakers and public administrators in the sector of urban planning and design. Consortium partners have a vast experience in providing consultations for better decision-making, thus the policy briefs will include information on addressing barriers, leveraging institutional resources, etc., regarding the implementation of innovative technologies in better urban planning and design practices.

A living document (UP2030 Publications & Events) (Figure 4) as a repository will be delivered to the consortium to help the monitoring of the dissemination of the project as regards to publication submitted and participation to various events. In addition, this living document aims to inform on future events relevant to the project.

A	Partner	Publication Title	Date of Publication	Open Access Status (Yes/No)	Citation	URL link (if any)	Notes (if any)
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							
13							

Figure 4 UP2030 Publications&Events

2.2.2 Dissemination Guidelines

Dissemination Activity Guidelines

To ensure the effectiveness of communication and dissemination efforts, it is important to follow the guiding principles below:

- Carry out activities in a timely manner.
- Follow the project’s visual identity guidelines (provided by DreVen in a dedicated document)
- Use accurate information.
- Ensure that messages are interesting to the target audience(s).

- Make sure that activities are appropriate in terms of resources spent, timing, and expected outcomes.

To evaluate and potentially adjust the dissemination plan, it is important to ask the following guiding questions:

- Do the actual results still meet the initially anticipated needs of a specific target group?
- Are there any new or emerging stakeholders that need to be considered?
- Have you chosen the appropriate measures for the right audience?
- What have been the concrete follow-up actions/results of certain dissemination measures?
- Have novel or unexpected results emerged? If so, how can they be effectively disseminated?

2.3 Individual Dissemination Plans

The whole consortium is fully engaged in creating awareness, understanding, and interest about the project. By integrating individual dissemination plans into the broader dissemination strategy, UP2030 can ensure that its research results and knowledge are effectively communicated to a wide range of stakeholders, maximizing the impact of its work.

For better organization and alignment, a dedicated document (UP 2030 Individual Dissemination Plan, Figure 5) will be distributed to the partners three times in the duration of the project (at the beginning of each year) and will be thoroughly checked at the end of each year.

In this document, all partners are asked to state what types of dissemination activities they will carry out to maximise the impact of UP2030. Partners are strongly encouraged to carry out these activities at least once during the year, except if there is a specific reason not to and which they should communicate with the D&C leader.

UP2030		Please add an 'X' on the types of dissemination activities you will carry out in 2023.						
Partner No.	Partner acronym	Description on the partner's website	Twitter post(s)	LinkedIn post(s)	Facebook post(s)	Announcement through the partner's organisation newsletter	Publication(s)	Event participation/organisation
P1	FRAUNHOFER							
P2	ADELPHI							
P3	BH							
P4	DC							
P5	GreenAdapt							
P6	ICA							
P7	ISOCARP							
P8	TSPA							
P9	TUD							
P10	UIC							
P11	GGGI							
P12	ICLEI							
P13	RCities							
P14	UCCRN							
P15	AQUATEC							
P16	CETAQUA							
P17	LIF							
P18	LNEC							
P19	MDAT							
P20	METU							
P21	USTUTT							
P22	VUB							
P23	CERTH							

Figure 5 UP2030 Individual Dissemination Plan

UP2030 will leverage the existing channels of its partners who will activate them to enhance outreach, increase visibility of the project, and improve communication and dissemination efforts. With the

contributions of all partners, UP2030 will create an exhaustive list in UP2030 Individual channels of the partners (Figure 6) to provide an overview of other channels/tools that will be used to multiply the content and outcomes.

All partners are requested to indicate their organization's available channels and social media feeds by adding an 'X' to the corresponding boxes. Where possible, partners provide the link, name, or social tag for each channel.

UP2030		Please indicate your organization's available channels and social media feeds by adding an 'X' to the corresponding boxes. Where possible, please provide the link, name or social tag for each channel.						
Partner No.	Partner acronym	Website	Twitter	Linkedin	Facebook	Newsletter	Journals	Other (please specify)
P1	FRAUNHOFER							
P2	ADELPHI							
P3	BH							
P4	DC							
P5	GreenAdapt							
P6	ICA							
P7	ISOCARP							
P8	TSPA							
P9	TUD							
P10	UIC							
P11	GGGI							
P12	ICLEI							
P13	RCities							
P14	UCCRN							
P15	AQUATEC							
P16	CETAQUA							
P17	LIF							
P18	LNEC							
P19	MDAT							
P20	METU							
P21	USTUTT							
P22	VUB							
P23	CERTH							

Figure 6 UP2030 Individual channels of partners

Individual dissemination plans can be integrated into the broader dissemination strategy in the following ways:

- **Collaboration and Coordination:** Ensure that the individual dissemination plans are aligned with the overall dissemination strategy of UP2030. This can be achieved by coordinating with each individual partner and making sure that it aligns with the goals and objectives of UP2030.
- **Knowledge sharing:** Encourage partners to share their findings and knowledge with each other, as well as with external stakeholders. Share, where useful, Specific guidelines for all partners.
- **Evaluation:** Regularly evaluate and share with the partners the effectiveness of individual dissemination plans and the overall dissemination strategy. This will help identify what is working well and what needs to be improved, and will enable the dissemination strategy to be adapted and refined as necessary.

2.4 Synergies with the other projects and Initiatives

Task 6.1 within WP6 will contribute to achieve important outcomes of the project:

- To engage the Mission cities in adopting the 5UP socio-technical framework
- To support results, validated in the UP2030 pilots, to mainstream climate neutrality in their built and natural environment
- To disseminate to ICLEI and RCities network members through the organisations' channels.

The Service Platform (WP5) can support this objective, as it will use the 5UP framework the backbone of the process-based approach to support the cities along their climate resilience and neutrality journey. Hence, through this Service Platform the UP2030 project will share all the knowledge, methodologies, tools and guidelines with cities beyond the project. ICLEI and Rcities as the two city networks will disseminate the project outcomes with their members through the organisations' channels as well as through major events (i.e., European Resilience Forum).

The relation with Mission initiatives and relevant projects is supported by dissemination activities that contribute to the UP2030 specific objectives, and in particular to SO5:

- ***SO5. Share broadly the lessons of success and levers to overcoming implementation barriers. Support replication beyond the project's scale in collaboration with the Mission while demonstrating how the solutions contribute to European policy and strategy implementation.***

UP2030 as part of the Mission family of projects will have the opportunity to disseminate its findings to an enlarged pool of cities part of the Mission creating synergies with the urban planning and design cluster, by contributing to the Mission aim to reach 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030. Hence, the Service Platform will seek collaboration and potential integration into the Cities Mission Implementation Platform, so cities can make use of the innovative outcomes from the UP2030 project.

Moreover, the project plans to create synergies with the Mission projects (and other EU outlets/marketplaces) to optimise use of resources and maximise impact. The UP2030 project will seek to build synergies with other relevant projects (e.g. NetZeroCities, Re-Value, CLIMABOROUGH) and initiatives (e.g. Smart Cities Marketplace, Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, DIGITAL program, etc.), in EU and beyond, focused on climate action in cities. Importantly, the project will seek collaboration with projects and partners involved in the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, building on those partners (such as ICLEI, Deltares), which are part of Mission Adaptation projects.

A specific task of WP6, T.6.4 Collaboration with the Mission and related projects is led by ICLEI to achieve this goal. T6.4 will provide specific actions to promote the collaboration according to the EU indications (EU 2020, Report of the Mission) [4]. The Task T6.4 will provide the landscape of the relevant stakeholders to collaborate with and will set a roadmap for the implementation of this collaboration. More specifically, this roadmap will serve to set the framework for the collaboration among the above-mentioned community of practice by setting three main pillars:

- the long-term objectives of this collaboration (during the lifetime of the project),
- the short-term objectives (these objectives will be set annually) and
- an indicative timeline and action plan for the implementation of the framework

3 Communication Plan

Developing a comprehensive communication plan is essential for any research project that aims to have a high impact, particularly when it involves multiple partners, stakeholders, and audiences. The goal of such a plan is to ensure that research outcomes reach their intended audiences and effectively engage them in the project's goals and objectives.

To achieve this, a systematic approach to planned communication activities throughout the project's duration must be developed. This refers to identifying key target audiences, customizing messaging and content for each audience, and leveraging a variety of communication channels to reach them.

UP2030 will focus on informing, promoting, and communicating project activities and results from the start of the action until the end, with the aim of reaching the general public as well.

3.1 Communication Objectives

The specific objectives of the UP2030 communication Plan are to:

- Create awareness, understanding and interests about the scope, objectives and results of the project
- Promote the innovative character and unique part of up2030
- Raise awareness about the project activities that will contribute to climate neutrality
- Increase the visibility of the project and its activities
- Show the successful stories of the projects' partnership
- Inform citizens/residents about climate emergencies in cities, call them to action to contribute to the transformation of their city to climate neutrality and give guidance on how to do so

3.2 Communication target audiences and messages

Identifying the target audience is a crucial aspect of developing a communication strategy that effectively engages with stakeholders and maximizes the impact of research outcomes. The target audience for communication are:

- Citizens
- Vulnerable & disadvantaged/marginalized groups
- Multipliers (such as local/national press etc.)

Furthermore, key messages are adapted to each target audience, and will be refined over the course of the project.

Specific communication opportunities related to target audiences and key messages are identified in the following table (Tab. 2):

<p>TARGET I Citizens</p>	<p>This audience includes members of the general public who may be impacted by the research outcomes and may have varying degrees of knowledge or interest in the topic of the project. They can include residents of a specific geographic area or members of a particular community.</p>	<p>Pedestrian & cyclist associations, neighborhood associations, elderly, women, children.</p>	<p>“UP2030 provides innovative tools and methods to encourage inclusive citizen participation and promote citizens to adopt sustainable behaviors to minimize their environmental footprint and contribute to the cities’ transitions .”</p>	<p>UP2030 sees citizens as an integral part of the transition as they shall become agents of change through their sustainable behavioral shifts and lifestyle decisions. Citizen engagement is more meaningfully facilitated at the neighborhood scale. UP2030 has the ambition to demonstrate new operational ways for engaging citizens effectively in the entire process – from needs assessment and early visioning through to co-design, implementation, and evaluation – recognizing that participation takes time, resources, and requires capacity building. UP2030 delivers tangible ways to secure active participation of citizens and stakeholders in the co-creation of urban planning and design practices, which strengthens local democracy and produces strategies based on the citizens’ actual needs. To reach this audience, activities might include hosting public forums or town hall meetings, creating social media campaigns to promote the project, and engaging with local media outlets to promote awareness of the project.</p>
<p>TARGET L Vulnerable & disadvantaged / marginalized groups</p>	<p>This audience includes specific sub-groups within the general public who may be disproportionately impacted by the research outcomes.</p>	<p>Disabled people's organizations, organizations for women, minorities and people in precarious conditions</p>	<p>“UP2030 provides innovative tools and methods to encourage inclusive citizen participation and promote citizens to adopt sustainable behaviors to minimize their environmental footprint and contribute to the cities’ transitions”.</p>	<p>UP2030 will focus on identifying and engaging vulnerable target groups – including through the proposed LAAs. It will identify what are the entry points to “converse” with different groups, as their primary drivers might not always be climate neutrality per se. However, neutrality can be an important co-benefit of their primary interests (e.g., energy costs, noise pollution, accessibility and so on). UP2030 will support pilot cities be deliberate towards spatial justice outcomes. UP2030 will build local capacity to co-design spatially just and procedurally fair policies and to mobilize citizens in innovative ways, harnessing their tacit knowledge to enhance spatial justice in “left-behind places” at regional and local scales. Urban planning and design become more effective and efficient when all genders are empowered to participate as equals in information sharing and generation, education and training, technology transfer, organizational development, financial assistance, policy development.</p>

Table 2 UP2030 Target Groups for Communication

3.3 Communication Tools and Activities

The following communication activities will be carried out throughout the lifespan of the project:

- **Visual identity**

UP2030's visual identity will be designed in M1 of the project. It will include the project logo and color palette that will be used in all the dissemination and communication activities of UP2030. Project materials (e.g., deliverables, papers, etc.) will be prepared following these identity guidelines in order to achieve the overall homogeneity of the project. Project templates, such as templates for deliverables and PowerPoint presentations, will also be prepared and distributed to partners.
- **Project website**

A project website will be designed and developed, and will act as UP2030's main communication tool. It will provide information about the project's objectives and activities and special effort will be made to provide access and customize content to the stakeholders of interest (including vulnerable groups). It will be maintained and updated regularly and will also have a dedicated page for regular (rota-based) blog posts prepared by the consortium partners regarding innovations in the project domains. The website will include access to the Story Maps as these are developed.
- **Social Media**

UP2030 aims to build a strong online presence in the most commonly used Social Media Platforms (Twitter and LinkedIn) to extend its circle of influence and reach out to a wider audience.
- **e-Newsletters and Email Campaigns**

e-newsletters will be prepared when key results of the project have been delivered in order to broadcast them to relevant stakeholders. In addition, project messages will be communicated to a targeted pool of contact points via emails, since this tool is deemed as a highly effective measure of engagement, especially when promoting events and outcome among different domains.
- **Press Releases**

Press releases will be produced when relevant pieces of news will be available in the project, especially targeting local and European electronic media.
- **Innovation Portfolio**

High-impact success stories deriving from the UP2030 solutions will be collected and presented to the public in a dedicated publication.
- **Comms. Kit**

Promotional material, such as brochures and posters, will be designed and distributed in every given opportunity. Printed material, it will be kept to a minimum or will be environmentally friendly in an effort to reduce the project's environmental footprint and also promote the project's vision.

3.3.1 Visual Identity

The visual identity of a project aims to facilitate its dissemination activities and ensure consistency in the communication of its objectives and results. In the context of UP2030, the visual identity consists of a logo, a specific colour palette and banners, which were all created at the early stages of the project. These will be shared to be partners through the SharePoint of the project, in order to facilitate them in their

communication activities in the lifespan of UP2030. Guidelines regarding the visual identity of the project will also be prepared by the WP6 leader, DreVen, in order to ensure that all partners use some common rules when communicating UP2030.

- **Colour Palette**

The colours used for the dissemination of a project plays a pivotal role in its recognisability to the public, increasing it up to 80%¹. For this reason, the UP2030 consortium took into sincere consideration the colour identity of the project and decided that it would have three (3) main colours; light green, blue and purple. This colour palette will be used for all purposes relevant to the project, from dissemination material to project deliverables.

Figure 8 UP2030 colour palette

- **Logo**

UP2030's logo is designed based on the colour palette presented above. There are two versions of the logo, the main version and the simplified one to be used in documents, both of which present the title of the project. When designing the logos, the main visions behind them were the following:

- The UP2030 project focuses on cities and therefore cities are depicted on the top of the logo (main version)
- UP is short for "urban planning" & "cities going upwards" (main and simplified version)
- The arrow symbolises the acceleration of the cities' socio-technical transition (main and simplified version)
- All in all, the logo accomplishes to successfully communicate UP2030's main vision, i.e., the achievement of cities' socio-technical transition to meet their Mission targets.

¹ <https://www.colorcom.com/research/why-color-matters>

Figure 9 UP2030 logos (main version and simplified version)

The UP2030 logo will play an essential role on the visual identity of the project. It will be reflected in all external communication occasions as it is conceived as the main visual messenger of the project and aids recollection and recall. The two versions of the UP2030 logo were shared in a dedicated folder of the project's MTeams SharePoint in order for every partner to have access to them. Partners should determine when it is appropriate to use each logo, but they should always ensure that they use the right size and resolution for their promotional activities. It is important to note that the logo should never be altered in any way or rotated.

Moreover, since UP2030 has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme, it is imperative that each material used in the dissemination process includes a copy of the EU emblem and a text with the following statement:

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EUROPEAN UNION or the EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

The emblem can be found on the EU website: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en.

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 10 EU emblem

- **Project banner**

An UP2030 banner was created in the first project month in order to be used on the social media accounts of the project (i.e., Twitter, LinkedIn). The banner uses the colour palette presented above and was designed so as to catch the attention of stakeholders and other people who may happen to stumble upon the project.

The main objective of the banner is to become the first point someone notices when they enter UP2030's social media accounts. Therefore, it is essential to capture the visitor's interest in mere seconds and encourage them to stay on the pages for further browsing. To this end, it needs to be characterised by its uniqueness and appeal to viewers.

Apart from social media, this banner can be used in any other communication activity carried out by the consortium partners and thus, it is available on the project's SharePoint in the folder dedicated to the visual identity of UP2030.

Figure 11 UP2030 banner

3.3.2 Project Templates

As already mentioned above, a set of templates has been designed aiming to ensure the consistency of the project’s visual identity throughout its lifespan, as well as facilitate the monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by the consortium. These templates were shared among all partners through e-mail communication and via UP2030’s MTeams Sharepoint.

The templates created by M3 are the following:

- Template for project deliverables
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for press releases
- Template for the preparation of blog articles
- Template for requesting consent in activities participation
- Template for general uses

The template used for deliverables consists of a front page, which includes the full title of the project and the titles of the deliverable and the WP this deliverable belongs to. The logo is also available and takes a significant part of the page. In addition, the EU emblem is presented, followed by the funding disclaimer. The second page displays main document information, the documented history of the deliverable, as well as copyright disclaimers. A table of contents, figures and tables is provided, along with a table describing all document acronyms and guidelines for references’ provision.

Figure 12 UP2030 deliverable template

A template for PowerPoint presentations was designed by DreVen following UP2030’s visual identity guidelines. It was distributed to all partners and was already used in the kick-off meeting, when consortium

partners presented their duties and responsibilities for the project. This PowerPoint template will be used for any internal and external communication.

Figure 13 UP2030 presentation template

A special template was designed for the dissemination of UP2030 related content to the media (press release template) and through the website (blog article template).

Figure 14 UP2030 press release template

Figure 15 UP2030 blog article template

Numerous engagement activities will take place through the lifespan of the project and for this reason, in order to conform with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) protecting stakeholders' personal data, a consent form template was designed by UP2030's legal partner LIF. Partners organising an activity that requires participation are obliged to distribute this consent form to the participants.

Dear Madam/Sir,

You have been invited to **[insert description of the relevant activity here]** under the framework of the European project Urban Planning and design ready for 2030 (UP2030). UP2030 aims to guide cities through the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality ambitions. It will do so by enabling a quantum leap from a 'business as usual' project-by-project decarbonisation approach to a vision-driven, strategy-based approach that is anchored on sound projects and renewed policy development.

With your participation you will make a substantial contribution to the implementation of **[please insert detailed explanation of the relevant task for which we invite participants; the overall procedure, its aim, how the outputs will be used and for what purpose afterwards, and how the person's participation will feed into the UP2030 project implementation].**

My participation will involve:

- Example: questionnaire/ completed plan/graphic by expert.
- What will I be required to do? [Example: assessment, policy/ tool development, urban planning]
- Where will this take place?
- How often will I have to take part, and for how long? [Example: for initial implementation; returning for second assessment]
- When will I have the opportunity to discuss my participation? [Debriefing]

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission and Government of the Netherlands. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation programme under the grant agreement of 101096405.

UP2030 Consent Form

1. Consent form

I have been provided with information about the task and my rights as a participant.

In relation to this task:

- I agree to take part in the **[specify the task e.g., workshop]** as a participant and complete all the exercises that aim to understand the end user's needs and objectives, which will be linked to the **[e.g. UP2030 prototypes in order to enable the design and implementation of tools, maps, etc.]**
- I agree that my personal data which is gathered in the course of and as the result of my participation in this task will be (i) collected and retained for the purpose of this project, and (ii) accessed and analysed by the **[insert partner name]** researchers for the purpose of conducting this **[insert the respective task name]**.

I acknowledge that:

- My participation is voluntary and that **I am free to withdraw from participation at any time without explanation.**
- My anonymity is guaranteed, and I will not be identified in publications or otherwise without my express written consent.
- I am aware of the legal ground on which the processing of my personal data is based, namely consent as per Art. 6 (1) (a) GDPR.¹
- **I am aware that I might withdraw my consent for the processing of my personal data, however without affecting the lawfulness of the processing prior to the withdrawal of consent.**
- I am aware that I have the following rights as a data subject, which I can exercise with the controller:
 - ✓ The right to access.
 - ✓ The right to rectification.
 - ✓ The right to erasure.
 - ✓ The right to restriction of processing.
 - ✓ The right to be informed about recipients after a request for rectification, erasure or restriction of processing.
 - ✓ The right to data portability.
 - ✓ The right to object.
 - ✓ The right not to be subjected to automated individual decision-making, including profiling.
 - ✓ To file a complaint to my national Data Protection Authority.
- I am aware that the controller and processor of my personal data provided in the context

Page 2 of 4

UP2030 Consent Form

of this participation is **[insert partner name and address]**. **[Partner name]** Data Protection Officer: **[Name]** (mail to **[email address to be added]**).

- I am aware that the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data are **[insert partners' names]**.
- I have been informed of the procedure on how to exercise these rights with the controller, namely: sending an e-mail to **[email address to be added]**.
- I am aware of the purposes for which my data is gathered and processed in this project, namely: **[insert the purpose of the respective task here]**.
- My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analysed by **[insert partner name]** researchers for the purpose of implementing this project. My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101096405.

In order to exercise your rights, as far as this task is concerned, you may contact the Project Management Office at **[email address to be added]**.

By signing this document, I agree to:

participate in **[insert the relevant task e.g., this workshop]** under the terms set out above and

the processing of my personal data,

appear in pictures taken at the event (for project communication and reporting activities).

My signature confirms that I accept and understand these conditions without reservation.

Date & Place

Signature

Contact

Name, Surname, Organization, Role in the project, Email

Page 3 of 4

Figure 16 UP2030 Consent form

Lastly, a document template for general uses was also created to be used by partners for UP2030 activities that are not relevant to the ones mentioned above.

Figure 17 UP2030 General use template

3.3.3 Social Media Presence

Social Media will play a key role in the dissemination process of UP2030. From the first month of the project, a Twitter and a LinkedIn account were created and shared to the public in an effort to raise awareness, increase visibility and interaction with contacts and receive useful inputs from stakeholders.

In addition, a social media strategy was developed in order to maximise impact deriving from the project. The UP2030 social media accounts will be updated regularly by DreVen and the posts will include content regarding innovations on the domain of urban planning and design, information about events the partners may organise or participate in, relevant initiatives, etc. Even though DreVen is the administrator of these social accounts, all partners are encouraged to share with DreVen interesting content to be published. The main goal of these posts will be

to gain attention from key stakeholders, as well as to extend the outreach of the project to additional potential stakeholders.

It should also be pointed out that the social media accounts of the project will follow relevant initiatives and contribute to the dissemination of their key achievements, with the aim to maximise our collaboration.

- LinkedIn URL page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/up2030-he>
- Twitter account URL page: https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE

Figure 18 UP2030 LinkedIn account

Figure 19 UP2030 Twitter account

3.3. 4 Website

UP2030’s website constitutes one of the main communication channels, since it allows stakeholders to stay up-to-date with the development and results of the project. Its content includes information about the objectives and the pilot use cases of UP2030. Moreover, visitors have access to the main public deliverables and documents, and other dissemination material, such as brochures, newsletters and posters. In addition, the website provides relevant content, e.g. news and events, in an effort to encourage stakeholder engagement.

In more detail, the UP2030 website will consist of the following indicative pages:

- ▽ Home

- ▽ About
 - Project
 - Mission
 - Relevant Initiatives
- ▽ Use cases
- ▽ Library
 - Publications
 - Deliverables
 - Communication Kit
- ▽ Consortium
- ▽ News & Events
- ▽ Contact Us

A more detailed description of the objectives and content of UP2030's website will be provided in deliverable "D6.3 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 1".

3.3.5 Events & Publications

Participation and organisation of several events is foreseen throughout the lifespan of the project in order to boost visibility of both consortium and project results. By attending conferences, workshops and other events, the consortium partners will disseminate information regarding UP2030 through presentations and at the same time will acquire knowledge about current urban planning and design trends. Furthermore, by participating in a wide variety of events, partners will have networking opportunities with researchers and stakeholders, and will also stay up-to-date with the advances in the domain of the project.

In addition, several publications will be produced by partners in order to disseminate research findings resulting from the project. These publications will constitute of papers to relevant peer-reviewed journals and will be carried out during the whole lifespan of UP2030.

Numerous events for partners to participate in and journals for partners to submit publications to have already been identified. A living document providing such information will be distributed to partners by DreVen in order to monitor such types of activities carried out by the partners.

3.3.7 Press Kit

A press kit will be developed and distributed to all partners by DreVen with the aim to use it through a variety of mass media channels. It will include information about the project through a factsheet, an UP2030 overview presentation, a brochure and a poster. UP2030 partners decided to prepare different

types of promotional material aiming to reach all target audiences. Additional materials may be produced according to the project's needs. The press kit will be distributed to stakeholders in digital form, as well as in printed copies. The partners will certainly make an effort to reduce the environmental impact of the project and for this reason printed copies will be limited.

3.3.8 Newsletter & Press release

Newsletters constitute an extremely efficient tool used to encourage stakeholders' engagement by distributing information about the findings of the project, relevant events, publications, etc. Therefore, there will be a special registration form on the project website, where interested visitors can sign up to receive UP2030's newsletters whenever news is available in the project.

In addition, to maximise the project's dissemination on the media, the consortium will prepare press releases to promote intermediate results and important milestones of UP2030. They will be disseminated by each partner through their networks and will be available on the project website.

4 Gender dimension in UP230 dissemination and communication strategy

The gender dimension of the UP2030 dissemination must be considered before, during and after all dissemination and communication activities, to ensure that the strategy of the project as a whole is gender-sensitive and inclusive.

These recommendations are based on the [Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication](#), published by the European Institute for Gender Equality [6], and on the [Gender in EU-funded research toolkit](#), published by the European Commission [7].

The requirements needed to integrate a gender-inclusive strategy within dissemination and communication are being developed by Mapping for Change (MfC), the partner responsible for assuring the UP2030 approaches take due consideration of gender perspectives according to the project Gender Situation Analysis and Needs Assessment (GSANA).

4.1 Communication teams

A first step towards a gender-sensitive dissemination plan is to guarantee gender balance in all communication teams across the consortium and, within those teams, to ensure that women and men have equal representation in decision-making positions.

Beyond the general gender analysis of the teams conducted by MfC, each member of the consortium should internally assess their team composition and guarantee that tasks are fairly distributed amongst people of different genders, for example, by establishing a rotating schedule for the design of dissemination materials or by setting up a system for their co-creation instead of relying on a single person. This increases the chances that multiple points of view are included in the dissemination material and minimises the risk of biased representations and/or language.

4.2 Communication channels

In order to reach as wide a population as possible, teams must use diverse communication channels that reach people of every gender identity, including social media platforms, radio, television, and print media.

It is known that there are differences in social media platforms usage between women and men (statistics found during the literature review do not include other gender identities), as shown in Figure 20 below. Therefore, it is recommended that similar posts are shared in more than one social media platform.

Figure 20 Global Social Media Statistics — DataReportal — Global Digital Insights

Moreover, it is recommended that the visuals and language used for each specific event is adapted to different social media platforms to increase the chances that the posts are equally visible across platforms. There is plenty of information about cross-posting and adapting posts (usually from a marketing point of view, but applicable to dissemination of events) online that could be used as a guide - see example [here](#).

Ideally, for specific events for which broad participation of the community is desired, a detailed local gender analysis of the target audience should be conducted to better understand their communication preferences and design the communication strategy accordingly. Whilst useful as a general guide, the statistics presented above do not accurately reflect local, small-scale social media usage preferences which may greatly influence the gender balance of a local intervention.

4.3 Gender-sensitive language and images

Gender-sensitive language must be used in all communications, in a way that addresses the different needs, interests, and perspectives of all genders*

**According to the European Institute for Gender Equality [5], gender-sensitive language is attained when women and men -and those who do not conform to the binary gender system - are addressed through language as persons of equal value, dignity, integrity and respect.*

If possible, in order to minimise the risk of accidental gender discrimination through images and visuals, pictures of objects (e.g. a desk with a computer) should be preferred over pictures of people (e.g. a person sitting at a desk using their computer). In some cases, however, the use of images of people cannot (or shouldn't) be avoided. For those cases:

- All teams, both in internal and external communication, must avoid images (or language) that reinforce gender stereotypes and/or that assume gender when gender is unknown.
- They must remain aware of the risk of accidental omission of certain groups or genders, for example, by ensuring that women and men are equally represented in all the dissemination materials and using images of women and men in active roles that correspond to the target groups of the project.
- Additionally, the choice of images must ensure that there is no systematic subordination of a gender - often women - to another. For example, by balancing the number of images depicting women and men in positions of authority.

We recommend that all communication teams and members of the consortium carefully read the [Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication](#) published by the European Institute for Gender Equality [5], which contains additional valuable information on how to include gender mainstreaming in communication strategies.

4.4 Stakeholder engagement

When possible, teams should adopt a participatory approach to the development of the communication strategy, engaging stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, to ensure that the communication strategy reflects the diversity of the project's stakeholders, including gender, age, ethnicity, and socio-economic status. This includes but is not limited to:

- Surveying the use of different communication channels and the preferences of people of all genders in the local community.
- Ensuring that the communication strategy is accessible to marginalised groups, including women with disabilities, LGBTQ+ communities, and women living in rural areas.
- Including women's voices and perspectives in the communication strategy, highlighting their contributions to the project's success.

4.5 Monitoring and evaluation

Beyond the centralised monitoring performed by [teams in charge of dissemination in general and MfC], each team must perform periodic internal assessments to monitor and evaluate the communication strategy, to ensure that it is effective in reaching its intended audience and achieving its goals, including gender equality and inclusion.

5 Dissemination and Communication Indicators

The impact of the project will be evaluated using key performance indicators (KPIs) for each dissemination and communication activity. A wide variety of indicators has been deemed by the consortium as appropriate to assess the impact of dissemination and communication. Table x and table x present some of these indicators as planned for the communication and dissemination activities, respectively, from the beginning of UP2030.

Communication activity	KPI
Visual Identity	Prepared in M1
Project website	Online by M3 Unique visitors by M36: >4,000
Social Media	Number of posts: 1 per week Size of online community by M36: > 4,000
e-Newsletters and Email Campaigns	Total number of distributed e-Newsletters: 12 Total Mailing List Contact Points: >1,500
Press Releases	Total number of press releases: 4
Innovation Portfolio	Number of success stories: story maps for all cities
Communication Kit	Number of events to be distributed through by end of project >30

Table 3 Communication activities KPIs.

Dissemination activity	KPI
Scientific Publications	Publishing in Peer-Reviewed Journal articles > 30 Presenting in Scientific Conferences > 50 At least 1 special edition led by UP2030 guest editors in a high impact Journal
Technical Publications	Publishing Technical Publications >20 Presenting in Technical Conferences > 20
Workshops & Trainings	Workshops >10 in 8 different countries Training Tutorials >8; Webinars >10

Joint Activities with relevant Initiatives	<p>Relevant initiatives to establish links >15</p> <p>Co-organised events >20</p> <p>Fairs to Participate >20</p>
Source Code Repository	<p>Number of Publicly Available Deliverables (24)</p> <p>Source code: publish to >2 different repositories</p>
Policy briefs	<p>Policy recommendations & best practices > 11 (at least 1 per pilot)</p>

Table 4 Dissemination activities KPIs.

The consortium of the project will evaluate the impact of each dissemination and communication tool by using the dissemination activities reporting templates prepared by the dissemination leader. DreVen will ask all the partners to provide every three months of the project a report regarding all of the activities they have conducted and aim at promoting UP2030 to stakeholders and the general public.

A timeplan regarding all dissemination and communication activities will be constructed by DreVen, aiming to facilitate partners organise their dissemination related tasks in advance and thus to ensure they are achieved successfully. In order to design this timeplan, all partners need to fill out the template presented above regarding their individual dissemination activities, so that the dissemination and communication leader has a clear picture of the activities that can be carried out by the consortium each of the three years of the project.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the Target-Driven Dissemination and Communication Strategy of UP2030 project, providing a fundamental roadmap for one of the main UP2030 objectives that is to foster the UP-TAKING through knowledge transfer. It includes a comprehensive plan for dissemination and communication strategies for the project.

A target driven strategy has been conceived to engage both specific audiences such as policy makers and the scientific community through dissemination activities, and a broader audience including non-specialists, through public awareness and accessible language with communication tools and activities. Successfully applying the target-driven Communication and Dissemination Strategy here presented is critical to achieving the long-term scientific and societal impact of the project and to accomplish the main goal of WP6 that is the UP-TAKING of UP2030 results. It implies that key players (Section 1) support its implementation since the start of the project, leveraging through existing networks the potential outreach of project activities. Dissemination target audiences and messages are identified and specific activities proposed (Section 2). Similarly, the communication plan (Section 3) is structured according the objectives, target audience, and communication tools and activities, including a gender-sensitive and inclusive strategy (Section 4). The quality of communication and dissemination will be assessed through monitoring activities and key performance indicators (Section 5). The purpose of this deliverable is to guide the effective dissemination and communication of the project's goals and objectives, and the further steps needed for implementation. To this aim, a series of living documents is shared among all UP2030 partners the has communication and dissemination opportunities, players and tools, so to promote collaborations among the several partners of the projects, also in relation to their individual dissemination plans.

The implementation of this Target-driven Dissemination and Communication Strategy developed in this deliverable will further implemented in the D6.2 due at March 2024 (M15) and it will be monitored and reported in the following deliverables:

D6.3	Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 1
D6.4	Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2
D6.5	Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 3

References

- [1] European Commission, Guidelines for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities, in EU Grants: HE Programme Guide, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
- [2] EU REGULATION 2021/695 2021 establishing Horizon Europe-Article 39, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R0695&qid=1621434634235&from=EN>
- [3] Webinar session: Dissemination & Exploitation in Horizon Europe (9 June 2021), <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>
- [4] European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gronkiewicz-Waltz, H., Larsson, A., Boni, A., et al., *100 climate-neutral cities by 2030 - by and for the citizens: report of the mission board for climate-neutral and smart cities*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/46063>
- [5] European Commission. Horizon Europe - Dissemination and exploitation. Retrieved March 22, 2023, from https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-dissemination-and-exploitation_en#free-of-charge-dissemination-and-exploitation-services.
- [6] European Commission, Open Research Europe Platform, <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>
- [7] European Institute for Gender Equality, Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication: a resource for policymakers, legislators, media and anyone else with an interest in making their communication more inclusive, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2839/589287>
- [8] European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gender in EU-funded research : toolkit, Publications Office, 2014, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/74150>